

Dating the timbers from the ‘Sparrow-Hawk’, a shipwreck from Cape Cod, USA

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ABSTRACT

In 1626, a vessel making its way to Virginia was forced off course and damaged in a storm, which drove the ship onto the eastern shore of the Cape Cod peninsula, Massachusetts. Onboard were two English merchants and some servants and farmers, many of whom were Irish. In 1863, a storm exposed the weathered remains of a vessel at Old Ship Harbor. At the time, it was hailed as the same ship that had brought the Virginia-bound passengers to Plymouth in 1626. Recent wiggle-match C14 dating and dendrochronology suggests that this is indeed a ship from the early seventeenth century.

1. Introduction

“There was a ship, with many passengers in her and sundrie goods, bound for Virginia.” (Bradford, 1899: 261). So wrote Governor Bradford of the infant Massachusetts Bay colony in his journal in 1626 (Bradford, 1899).

He went on to describe the arrival and wrecking of a ship carrying English and Irish settlers to the New World (Fig. 1). He reported that the vessel ran aground on the eastern shore of Cape Cod, near the modern town of Orleans, and could not be repaired. Two English merchants, John Fells and John Sibsey, who hoped to establish a tobacco plantation, were on board with their servants and some farmers, many of them Irish, whom they had recruited to people their colony. “The cheefe amongst these people was one Mr. Fells and Mr. Sibsey, which had many servants belonging unto them, many of them being irish.” (Bradford, 1899: 264). The passengers and crew were allowed to stay at Plymouth Plantation while they awaited passage south. They were allocated some land so that they could earn their keep and so that they would not be idle during their stay (Holly, 1969; Wilkins, 2011).

In 1863, a storm exposed the remains of a small ship at a place named Old Ship Harbor. This find was given the name *Sparrow-Hawk* (by an enterprising local landowner) and it was, at the time, hailed as the same ship that had brought the Virginia-bound passengers to Plymouth in 1626. The timber remains were lifted and the wreck was assembled and exhibited at several places in the region, even on Boston Common, in

1865. At the time, the remains were described by Charles W. Livermore, who stated, “Her keel is of English elm” (Holly, 1969: 9). The rest of the remains are oak. Since 1889, the remains have been under the care of the Pilgrim Hall Museum in Plymouth, Massachusetts, where it was also exhibited for many years.

It is intriguing that this particular seventeenth-century story was quickly attached to these physical remains, as there was no immediate evidence for the date of the vessel and any number of ships and boats have been wrecked on the shores of Cape Cod. Even before the arrival of the famous *Mayflower* in 1620, ships from Europe were exploring these waters. After the *Mayflower* journey and the settlement of Plymouth, numerous settlements became established along the New England coast, increasing maritime traffic to and from the region. Second, it is important to distinguish and clarify the fact that *Sparrow-Hawk* was the name ascribed to the shipwreck in 1863, but was certainly not the name of the ship originally. In a professional archaeological setting, we would normally name a wreck after the find spot. However, this wreck has been known as *Sparrow-Hawk* for so long, and if we propose a different name for it, we run the risk of confusing the issue.

In this paper, we are trying to establish whether this ship could be a specific vessel known from historical sources, but the sources do not tell us what the vessel carrying tobacco farmers from England in 1626, had been called. We are therefore continuing to use the made-up name from 1863 simply because it is the well-known label that has been attached to this wreck for more than 150 years (Wilkins, 2011). For example, in his

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thesis on the formative years of the American tobacco trade, Scott Tucker (2017) discusses the evidence for the possibility that the *Sparrow-Hawk* remains are indeed the same ship that Bradford mentions in his diary, and he states:

“Further, some of the physical evidence has been taken on assumption of accuracy based on the 19th century reports. An example of this is the description of wood used, said to be English elm and English oak. Modern microscopy is incapable of this sort of accuracy in wood speciation, so to assume the qualifier of ‘English’ here is suspicious at best. Given the importance of this vessel in modern archaeological study, the opinion of this author is that new analysis using modern scientific methods be undertaken on *Sparrow[-]Hawk*. The significance of this vessel to this study lies in it being potentially an example of an early vessel used in the tobacco trade, providing physical evidence of the state of shipbuilding technology at an early point in the English colonial experience. An affirmation or negation of the remains as an early English trade vessel would be deeply useful for myriad reasons.” (Tucker, 2017, 71).

A dendrochronological analysis was the next step, in the study of the so-called *Sparrow-Hawk*. Two questions could be asked using scientific analyses of the timbers from this wreck: what is the dating of the find, and where did these timbers grow?

2. Dating the timber

2.1. Sampling

In January 2018, we had the opportunity to visit Pilgrim Hall in Plymouth, to take samples from the ship timbers, for dendrochronological analysis. The aim was to confirm scientifically, through tree-ring analysis, whether this ship is indeed a European ship from the seventeenth century. Dendrochronology is the science of analyzing the pattern of wide and narrow rings in trees. The tree’s growth is like a fingerprint of the climate in the place and time that the tree grew. By comparing the tree-ring pattern between trees, we can identify the time in which the tree grew and we can see which trees are most alike. This allows us to date historic timber, and also to identify where the timber grew. For a reliable result, however, trees that grew for at least 100 years are needed. This is to ensure that the pattern in the tree-rings is unique in time.

The study was done as part of the project Northern Europe’s timber resource – chronology, origin and exploitation (TIMBER). Timber in Northern Europe is being studied to develop a precise chronology for the material evidence for trade of timber from c. CE 1200 to 1700, to map the trade in this construction material, to show the regional and temporal fluctuations in timber exploitation and availability through time and to discover the origin of so-called ‘Baltic’ oak.

All the surviving timbers from the *Sparrow-Hawk* were examined, so that the best timbers for the dendrochronological analysis could be chosen and to make an initial assessment if construction features were

Fig. 1. John Foster & William Hubbard’s 1677 map of New England. [London: Printed by John Foster, 1677], Wine Hills version, map reproduction courtesy of the Norman B. Leventhal Map & Education Center at the Boston Public Library MHS image number 3715, (Foster, 1677).

consistent with a seventeenth-century date. Timbers from long-lived trees are sought, so that measurements from long series of tree-rings can be taken. Four surviving planks contained many narrow rings, so these were targeted for analysis (Fig. 2). The cut ends of three of these allowed access to the cross-section, with only a small degree of paring with a very sharp razor blade, to ensure that all the tree-rings were clearly visible (Fig. 3). Three plank fragments were sampled, by drilling to extract a core, but one of these was too fragmentary to allow reliable tree-ring measurement. One plank appeared charred, and an attempt to clean the end, to render the tree-rings visible, was not successful. The framing timbers were predominantly made from short-lived trees. There was one exception to this. The floor timber of the midships frame (the frame at the widest point in the hull) was made from a slower-grown, long-lived oak tree (Fig. 4). Cores from eight frames were taken (see Fig. 5). Finally, tree-rings were clearly visible on one end of the keelson, and these were photographed for subsequent measurement. In all 16 timbers were sampled, either by coring or photography.

2.2. The tree-ring analysis

The images of the photographed timbers were calibrated according to the scale in the photos, and measured on the computer screen, using a measuring software called Able Image Analyzer. The cores were prepared with a razor blade to make the tree-rings clearly visible, and measurement was carried out using a moving digital stage under a stereo microscope. All measurements are recorded to an accuracy of ± 0.01 mm. A summary of the samples is given in Table 1. Two timbers, a plank and the midships floor timber, contain 141 and 169 tree-rings respectively. All other samples contain fewer than 100 tree-rings. There were 10 timbers with relatively few rings (between 24 and 71) and cross-matching of these has not been successful.

Two cross-matching groups have been identified in the remaining five timber series. These are illustrated in Fig. 6. A small group (group 1) consists of two timbers – the midships floor timber and a futtock (a framing timber from the side of the hull). A second group includes three planks. Averages of these two groups were made. There is no significant match between these two groups.

The data was also shared with many colleagues, to see if anyone could find the dating position for them. Attempts to date them using extensive datasets for oak for Northern Europe and for eastern North America initially proved unsuccessful. While some tentative positions appeared, there was no positive match.

2.3. Sampling for C14 wiggle-match

Radiocarbon dating is not normally useful for relatively modern materials, due to the large swings in the radiocarbon calibration curve. The traditional story of this wreck suggested that it dated to the early seventeenth century, but if the timbers were from a later wreck, the C14 analysis would give a very wide dating range.

However, because two of the samples are from long-lived trees, the possibility presented itself that if inner tree-rings were selected for C14 dating, we could bypass this problem, by dating carbon that is

Fig. 2. View of one of the plank fragments (2018.605.019) from the *Sparrow-Hawk* wreck (photo: Aoife Daly).

Fig. 3. Macro view of the cleaned and chalked end-grain of plank fragment 2018.605.019 (photo: Aoife Daly).

Fig. 4. The central floor timber (2018.605.040) from the *Sparrow-Hawk* ship. Three original holes for the ships trenails can be seen, and rough incised numbers probably from the 19th century. The hole left after extracting the core for dendrochronology is seen at lower left (photo: Aoife Daly).

Fig. 5. Sampling a crutch timber (2018.605.053) from the *Sparrow-Hawk* for tree-ring analysis (photo: Calvin Mires).

significantly older than the date of the felling of the tree.

Initially, two sub-samples were extracted: one from the outermost rings of the midships floor timber 2018.605.040 and another from the outer rings of plank 2018.605.029. The reason for this strategy was, on the one hand, to allow for a more informed selection of which tree-rings to select for the second pair of sub-sampling, and on the other to minimize unnecessary expense, if it was found that a wiggle-match was not likely to narrow down the calibrated dating. The results of these two initial datings gave very wide ranges but still suggested that the timber was from a ship that could indeed fit the story. So additional sub-samples

Table 1List of the dendrochronological samples from the *Sparrow-Hawk* timbers. The dendrochronological groups are listed.

filename	name	Number of rings	pith	sapwood	Bark?	conversion	Unmeasured outer rings	Average ring width (mm)	comment
Z2170019	Sparrow Hawk 2018 605 019 plank from photo	141	G	0	N	T	H1	1,14	Group 2
Z2170029	Sparrow Hawk USA 2018 605 040 center frame	169	V	0	N	O	H1	0,54	Group 1
Z217003a	Sparrow Hawk USA 2018 605 053 crutch inner core fragment	63	G	0	N	O	N	1,37	
Z217003b	Sparrow Hawk USA 2018 605 053 crutch outer core fragment	39	G	0	N	O	H3	0,80	
Z217004a	Sparrow Hawk USA D17 2018 605 020 plank fragment from photo	52	G	0	N	T	H1	1,08	
Z217005a	Sparrow Hawk USA D18 2018 605 021 plank NOT GOOD very fragile surface from photo	64	G	0	N	T	H1	0,71	
Z217006a	Sparrow Hawk USA D19 2018 605 022 plank from photo	71	G	0	N	T	H1	1,58	
Z217007a	Sparrow Hawk USA D2 2018 605 054 crutch	37	G	0	N	O	H1	2,27	
Z217008a	Sparrow Hawk USA D3 2018 605 013 plank inner core fragments	34	G	0	N	T	N	1,17	
Z217008b	Sparrow Hawk USA D3 2018 605 013 plank outer core fragment	66	G	0	N	T	H1	1,12	Group 2
Z2170099	Sparrow Hawk USA D4 2018 605 037 floor	50	G	7	N	O	N	1,96	
Z217010a	Sparrow Hawk USA D6 2018 605 029 plank	94	G	0	N	T	H1	1,00	Group 2
Z217011a	Sparrow Hawk USA D8 2018 605 101 futtock	30	G	0	N	O	H1	2,97	
Z217012a	Sparrow Hawk USA D9 2018 605 035 floor	24	G	0	N	O	H1	1,73	
Z217013a	Sparrow Hawk USA D12 2018 605 075 floor	24	G	0	N	O	H1	2,08	
Z217014a	Sparrow Hawk USA D13 2018 605 103 futtock	51	G	0	?	O	N	0,86	Group 1
Z2170159	Sparrow Hawk USA D15 2018 605 007 keelson from photo	33	G	0	N	O	H1	4,03	
	Sparrow Hawk USA D7 2018 605 028 plank								Not measured
Z217M001	Sparrow Hawk planks 3 timbers [Daly 2018] group 2	141						1,22	
Z217M002	Sparrow Hawk frames 2 timbers [Daly 2018] group 1	169						0,60	

Fig. 6. Two groups are identified dendrochronologically. Group 1 consists of two frames and group 2 consists of three planks (Illustration: Aoife Daly).

were extracted. The recently published calibration curve IntCal20 was used in this analysis (Reimer et al., 2020).

2.4. The C14 dating results

The individual results of the C14 analysis of all the sub-samples from the two ship timbers are available in full, in the supplementary material at [10.5281/zenodo.5840325](https://zenodo.org/record/5840325). In the following we describe the result of combining all these results (wiggle match).

2.4.1. Midships frame 2018.605.040

The core from this timber contained 169 heartwood tree-rings, and the core was taken at the heartwood/sapwood boundary. Thus, if we apply a sapwood statistic for England (Hillam et al., 1987) c. 10–55 rings might be missing to the bark edge. As mentioned above, the sub-sampling was done in two phases. The first (2018.605.040A) was taken from the outermost rings on the core (rings 164–169 (including both early and latewood)). The C14 dating result gave a very wide calibrated age range of 1479–1640 cal AD (Beta-516638: 330 ± 30 BP). Based on this result, a second sub-sample from the core (2018.605.040B)

was extracted from tree-rings from the inner part of the tree (rings 20–25 (including both early and latewood)). The C14 result of this sample suggests that these rings were formed in 1399–1450 cal AD (Beta-520554: 500 ± 30 BP).

As we know the number of rings (144) between these two sub-samples we can refine the calibration of the C14 results. This is illustrated in green in Fig. 7. It calculates that the most likely date for the formation of the outer rings is within the range CE 1547–1592. If the tree that was used to make this timber had grown in England, as the story suggests, then by applying the English sapwood estimate, the felling of the tree could have taken place in around CE 1556–1646.

2.4.2. Plank 2018.605.029

The core from this timber contained 94 tree-rings (plus one unmeasured partial ring outermost). No sapwood was observed on this plank during sampling, and we thus do not know how much of the outer wood was trimmed to shape the plank, when the ship was built. Thus, we must remember that the C14 analysis is telling us the date of the formation of the tree-rings, not the time of the felling of the tree. The sub-sampling of this plank was done in three phases. The first (2018.605.029A) was taken from the outermost rings on the core (rings 93–95 (including both early and latewood)). The C14 dating result gave again a very wide calibrated age range of 1420–1609 cal AD (Beta-

516637: 440 ± 30 BP). Based on this result, a second sub-sample was extracted from the core (2018.605.029B) from tree-rings from the inner part of the tree (rings 1–3 (including both early and latewood)). The C14 result of this sample suggests that these rings were formed in 1310–1426 cal AD (Beta-520555: 560 ± 30 BP). With these two results the wiggle match calculates that the most likely date for the formation of the outer rings is within the range CE 1420–1498. Due to the wide range of the second sub-sample from the inner rings of the plank sample (it hits a fourteenth century inversion in the calibration curve), a third sub-sample (2018.605.029C) was taken, this time from rings 33–37 (including both early and latewood). This result gave a range 1408–1455 cal AD (Beta-522292 480 ± 30 BP).

Again, as we know the number of rings between the three sub-samples we can refine the calibration of the C14 results. This is illustrated with purple in Fig. 7. The outer rings preserved in the plank were formed in the range CE 1475–1507. As mentioned above, the tree-ring curve from the core sample from plank 029 cross-matches with two other plank tree-ring curves from the wreck. Its position in the group shows that it does not contain the youngest rings of the three cross-matching planks (Fig. 6). The outermost ring on plank 019 was formed 12 years after the outermost on our C14 dated plank 029. Neither of these planks had any sapwood preserved. So using the evidence from the wiggle match analysis, we can allow for missing sapwood

Fig. 7. Diagram illustrating the combined results of the radiocarbon dating. The calibration is calculated using Oxcal (Bronk Ramsey and Lee, 2013, Oxcal v4.4.1 <https://c14.arch.ox.ac.uk/oxcal/>, accessed 17 august 2020). The grey meandering river is the radiocarbon calibration curve IntCal20 (Reimer et al., 2020) and the results of the modeled calibration of the C14 datings (wiggle-match) are in green for frame 040 and in purple for plank 029. The outermost preserved rings on frame 040 were probably formed in the period CE 1547–1592 (95% statistical confidence). The tree for the frame was felled probably in the end sixteenth or beginning of the seventeenth century. The outer preserved rings on the plank were formed CE 1475–1507 (95% statistical confidence) (Illustration: Oxcal v4.4.1 and Aoife Daly).

and the chronological position of plank 029 to say that the planks for the *Sparrow-Hawk* vessel are from trees felled after c. CE 1498.

3. The origin of the timber (provenance)

The second challenge of the scientific analysis of the timbers, was to try to identify the region where the trees used to build the ship had grown. If the ship in Bradford's account sailed from England, could we identify the timbers as of English origin?

3.1. The keel

Livermore stated that the keel is of English elm, but can we use this as an indication of the ship's origin? The elm, *Ulmus* sp., genus is geographically widespread and can have up to 45 different species from Asia, Europe and North America (Wheeler and Manchester, 2007). Wheeler and Manchester state that the ring-porous species have late-wood pore clusters in tangential bands, with the bands varying from straight to wavy. In the context of the elm keel from the so-called *Sparrow-Hawk*, Wheeler & Manchester state "There is considerable variation in Section *Ulmus* and for the most part considerable difficulty in distinguishing the species from one another" (Wheeler and Manchester, 2007: 336). For identifying the three European species *Ulmus* is characterized as a ring-porous wood and key characteristics include that in the late wood, the vessels and their associated axial parenchyma are in tangential bands. Of the three European species Fritz Schweingruber states that "the wood of the three *Ulmus* species (*U. campestris* L., *U. scabra* Mill., *U. laevis* Pallas) cannot be differentiated on the basis of anatomic characteristics" (Schoch et al., 2004, Schweingruber, 1990). For the North American *Ulmus rubra* the broad early wood zone might distinguish it apart from other *Ulmus* species. Unfortunately, there are no clear features of the wood anatomy of elm to allow us to identify with certainty whether the keel is English or otherwise, only that, as we also observed, the keel of *Sparrow-Hawk* is elm rather than another ring-porous deciduous wood.

3.2. Genetics

The possibility to use DNA analysis to identify the genetic signature of the timbers and thereby to be able to identify the timber provenance was a natural next step. A range of genetic markers have been developed to identify oak origin to the continental level (Schroeder et al., 2018). A sub sample was taken from the same timbers that were sub-sampled for the C14 dating. Unfortunately, no genetic material could be extracted from these two samples and this is most probably because the genetic material from the timbers is too degraded. The full details of the DNA analysis is described in Akhmetzyanov et al. (2020) and is not reiterated here.

3.3. Revisiting the dendrochronological analysis

As mentioned above, a tentative dating position was indicated for the tree-ring series from the dendrochronological analysis. Several colleagues (their names are listed in the acknowledgements), with whom the data was shared, independently suggested a dating position for the *Sparrow-Hawk* plank average (group 2 defined above (Fig. 6)). The correlations that emerged were not quite significant enough to allow this dating to be accepted unequivocally, however. In light of the results of the C14 dating of plank 2018.605.029, demonstrating that the outermost preserved rings were formed in the last decades of the fifteenth century (CE 1475–1507 (Fig. 7)), we can more confidently identify the dendrochronological position. There is a correlation for the group 2 average at the dating position CE 1359–1499. The significant correlations for this dating position appear with site chronologies from southern England (Table 2). The dendrochronological evidence points to an English origin for the trees used to make the planks for the wreck found

Table 2

List of correlations (*t*-value) between the average of the three tree-ring series from the *Sparrow-Hawk* planks (group 2) and diverse site chronologies.

Filenames	–	–	Group 2 planks Z217M001	
–	start	dates	AD1359	
–	dates	end	AD1499	
TUDORHS5	AD1399	AD1630	6.01	Southampton, Tudor House Museum, Bugle Street & Blue Anchor Lane, Tudor House, Hampshire (Miles et al., 2009)
NEWCHRCH	AD1359	AD1449	5.48	Wales, Powys, The Great House, Newchurch, Radnorshire (Miles and Haddon-Reece, 1996)
TOLST17	AD1349	AD1511	5.41	London, Hamlets Tower of London, St Thomas Tower (Tyers pers. comm.)
stvasq01	AD1352	AD1512	5.35	Cornwall, St Ciricus & St Julitta Church, St Veep (Arnold et al., 2005)
Crawley	AD1369	AD1494	5.25	Sussex, Crawley Hall at Singleton, 14 timbers (Tyers pers. comm.)
tmfasq01	AD1367	AD1539	5.23	Devon, Warleigh House, Tamerton, Foliot (Arnold et al., 2006)
ADD-T3	AD1369	AD1490	5.17	London, Croydon, Addington House 3 trees (Bridge, 1998)
bfbt5	AD1328	AD1453	5.13	Devon, Bridford Barton, Bridford, 5 timbers (C Tyers pers. comm.)
ARMYNAVY	AD1350	AD1500	5.11	Alton, Army and Navy Stores, 23 High Street, Hampshire (Miles and Worthington, 1999)
Portland	AD1377	AD1494	5.05	Portland Castle, Castleton, Dorset (Bridge, 2000)
GBM00007	AD413	AD1728	4.68	London, 1003 timbers (Sheffield University)
GBM00010	AD406	AD1594	4.64	Southern England, 320 timbers (Sheffield University)

at Cape Cod. Using a sapwood statistic for England (Hillam et al., 1987), the estimated felling of the trees used to make the planks can be placed at after CE 1510.

4. Discussion

Several details are made clear, from the wiggle-match C14 and dendrochronological analyses. Firstly, the two groups that are identified dendrochronologically, making a clear distinction between the frames and the planks, might not indicate different sources for the two timber types. The wiggle-match strongly suggests that the two groups are chronologically separate (Fig. 7). The earlier dating for the planks clearly indicates that considerable trimming of the original trees took place to make the planks. This is not unusual. Planks need to be made narrower towards the stem and stern, when forming the hull shape. The average growth rate, expressed in terms of the average tree-ring width, of the three planks from this wreck is just over 1 mm per year. If just 10 cm are trimmed from the edge of the plank, as many as 100 rings can have been removed.

The sapwood observed on the frames brings us closer to an accurate estimate of the date for the building of the ship. If the use of elm for the keel, which was a more common tradition in English shipbuilding than elsewhere, and the provenance of the planks as indicated by the dendrochronology, indicates that the vessel is of English origin, then we should use the sapwood statistic for English oak (Hillam et al., 1987). The range of sapwood years here is rather wide, with 95% of trees

containing 10 to 55 sapwood rings. The felling of the tree used to make the C14-dated frame took place in the range CE 1556–1646 (Fig. 8).

Although some naval shipyards seasoned timber before using it in the 17th century, most of the historical and archaeological evidence suggests that merchant ships were built of greener timber. Small yards could not afford to have capital tied up in timber for very long. Vessels like *Sparrow-Hawk* could also be built ad hoc, with a yard set up temporarily to construct a vessel. In this case, seasoned timber was not really an option. So it is unlikely that the timber used to build this vessel had been seasoned.

There is little if any evidence in the surviving timbers of any significant repairs. Repairs are usually indicated by oddly shaped pieces let into the edges of larger timbers, extra fastener holes, and cut marks on the planking faces of the frames, none of which were apparent when the timbers were examined. Very little of the planking survives, so there may have been smaller repairs or alterations that we cannot see. All of the timbers sampled for this project were chosen after examining the remains, and we are confident that they are all part of the original construction of the vessel.

The results indicate that this vessel *could* have been built before 1626 and thus *could* be the vessel that wrecked on Cape Cod, reported by Bradford.

The dating and provenance identification process has been a long, complicated but hugely worthwhile exercise. Even if it cannot confirm the identity of the vessel, the wiggle-matching suggests that it is unlikely that this vessel is later than the mid-seventeenth century. Traffic along this coast increased, from 1620 onward, but was still relatively light in comparison to European coasts, with proportionately fewer losses. The number of possibilities for the identity of this wreck has been substantially narrowed, since we can be reasonably sure it is not a ship from the eighteenth or nineteenth centuries. It is even less likely that one of the few other ships wrecked on Cape Cod before 1650 might be in the same spot as Bradford reported in 1626. There is nothing in the construction of the remains that would be out of place in a vessel of this date. The assembly of the backbone elements and the framing method can be seen in the remains of other smaller vessels from the seventeenth century from Northern European sites. An upper pump box (the moving piston in a type of pump commonly used on ships in the early modern period) found in the wreck survives, and this is identical in its form and features with the pump boxes found on the Swedish warship *Vasa*, which sank in 1628 (Hocker, 2011) (Fig. 9). By narrowing the likely date range, and combining it with the geographical and construction data, the statistical probability that this is a wreck other than the 1626 vessel has been significantly reduced. Did it strand a small group of would-be tobacco farmers in New England in that year? There is probably no way to determine that with certainty this far removed from the excavation of

Fig. 9. The pump boxes from A: *Sparrow-Hawk* and, for comparison, B: *Vasa* (a Swedish warship from 1628). (photo A: Pilgrim Hall Museum, Plymouth, Massachusetts. Photo B: Vasamuseet).

the find, but there is no reason to say it is definitively not that vessel.

When a wreck, readily identifiable as old by its weathering, was found in the place described by Bradford, it was no great leap by locals (who knew the story of the settlement of Massachusetts Bay pretty well, having been taught it in schools since the 1820s) to connect it to the 1626 ship. Although the analysis cannot prove that this is the ship of 1626, it does show that it is possible. By showing that the ship is built with English timber and is unlikely to be later than the mid-seventeenth century, it indirectly supports the identification. How many other early seventeenth-century English vessels are likely to have been lost in the same place?

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Aoife Daly: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition. **Fred Hocker:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Calvin Mires:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – review & editing.

Fig. 8. Diagram illustrating the combined results of the radiocarbon and dendrochronological dating. The position in time of the tree-ring curves from the planks is represented with grey bars. The estimated felling of the trees used for the planks, after 1510, is indicated in purple. The dating of the outermost preserved tree-rings from the frame, which was sampled at the heartwood to sapwood boundary, is shown using the results of the modeled calibration of the C14 analysis. The red vertical line marks the date of Bradford's account of the wrecking of a ship from England (Illustration: Aoife Daly).

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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